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Briefing

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Briefing on the Chişinău Declaration

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This briefing is issued by members of the [Agora group](#), an independent, pan-European platform committed to open dialogue, rigorous inquiry, and balanced, evidence-based debate on key issues concerning the integrity, resilience and effectiveness of the European Convention on Human Rights system.

Key messages

- The Chişinău Declaration reaffirms states' commitment to the European Convention on Human Rights and the independence of the European Court of Human Rights.
- It highlights migration-related challenges faced by some states, and their intention to explore “new approaches” to dealing with migration
- The Declaration does not change the text of the Convention. Nor does it identify any specific aspect of the ECHR system or the case law of the Court that prevents states from operating an effective migration enforcement regime.
- It calls for further guidance on how national authorities should apply the ECHR in specific migration contexts.
- Concern has been expressed that the Chişinău process signals the intention of some states to permanently narrow the protection of human rights for migrants, creating a two-tier system and opening the door to the erosion of protection for other groups in the future.

What is the Chişinău Declaration?

The [Chişinău Declaration](#) is a political declaration about the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR) system in the context of migration. It was adopted unanimously by the foreign ministers of the 46 member states of the Council of Europe at the annual meeting of its governing body, the Committee of Ministers, in Chişinău, Moldova, on 15 May 2026.

What is a political declaration?

Political declarations express the common position of member states and set the priorities of the Council of Europe. Declarations are not legally binding, i.e. they do not create enforceable obligations under international law. However, they carry significant political weight and can potentially influence the Court, as well as guiding domestic courts and national authorities.

Does the Declaration change the text of the ECHR itself?

No, the Declaration neither changes the text of the ECHR nor calls for any revision. States express their support for the independence of the Court and reaffirm their commitment to implementing the Convention and abiding by judgments of the Court.

To change the text of the ECHR, all 46 states would need to agree – and consent to be bound by – a Protocol to revise the Convention. There is no suggestion that this is being considered at present. [Experts](#) say that, based on previous experience, such a process could take several years.

How did the Declaration come about?

Last year, some states signalled their view that the Court unduly inhibits migration control and their intention to constrain the application of the Convention in the migration context, including in respect of Article 3, which prohibits torture and inhuman or degrading treatment. These views were expressed in an open letter signed by [nine states](#) in May 2025 and a statement issued by [27 states](#) in December 2025.

However, these initiatives did not command the support of all governments. Countries such as France, Germany, Spain and Turkey, which between them host [almost 60%](#) of people seeking asylum in Europe, did not endorse them.

In December 2025, the Secretary General convened an [informal conference](#) of justice ministers to discuss issues related to migration and the ECHR, which [launched](#) an unusually rapid process to draw up a political declaration for adoption in Chişinău.

The Declaration evolved after objective analysis of the Court’s case law by government legal experts from all 46 states and negotiation between state representatives.

Given its origins in the letter of nine and statement of 27 states, [concern](#) has been expressed that the Declaration is the first in the history of the Council of Europe that is motivated by a wish on the part of some states to narrow the application of rights for certain categories of people. The introduction of exceptions or differentiated standards would create a [hierarchy](#) of rights-holders entitled to differing levels of protection and open the door to the erosion of protection for other groups in the future.

What does the Declaration say about migration and human rights?

The Declaration sets out well-established principles in the application of Convention rights in the migration context. It does not identify any specific element of the ECHR or the Court's case law that prevents states from having an effective migration enforcement regime.

It underlines that, as the Court has repeatedly said, states have the “undeniable sovereign right to decide on and control foreign nationals' entry into and residence in their territory” and to pursue immigration control as a public interest. However, this must be done in accordance with the provisions of the Convention.

The Declaration affirms that removing a person to a state where they face a real risk of death, persecution or severe ill-harm is prohibited under international law (a principle known as *non-refoulement*).¹

It acknowledges that the right to private and family life (Article 8 ECHR) allows states to expel foreign nationals as long as a balance has been struck between individual rights and wider interests such as national security and public safety.

Given that states have primary responsibility for implementing Convention rights, the Declaration expresses appreciation for the Court's efforts to ensure that its case law is clear and consistent and that its interpretation of the Convention proceeds in a “careful and balanced manner”.

The Declaration outlines migration-related challenges faced by some states. These include difficulties in removing people charged with or convicted of serious offences. The Declaration also refers to the pressure created by processing large volumes of claims in “frontline” states and by the “instrumentalisation” of migration (see below).

It calls for greater co-operation between states to prevent irregular migration, promote returns, and confront human trafficking and migrant smuggling networks, as well as to counter and prevent misinformation about the Court's case law.

The Declaration says it is important that states can pursue "new approaches to managing migration" to address and potentially deter irregular migration, such as “return hubs” (offshore detention facilities), provided that they continue to fulfil their Convention obligations.

States call for further guidance in some areas. What are they?

States call for further guidance, including from the Court, about how national courts and authorities should apply Convention rights in two specific areas.

First, where a person challenges removal on the basis of a real risk that they would face inhuman or degrading treatment in the state to which they are being sent, either due to (i) prison conditions, i.e. conditions that cause intense distress or hardship, or (ii) “socio-economic factors”, i.e. where there is a serious risk that the person would fall into extreme destitution.

Secondly, the Declaration looks forward to guidance from the Court on how to apply Convention rights in the context of the “instrumentalisation” of migration. There is no agreed legal definition of instrumentalisation, but it generally [refers](#) to situations where third countries use people on the move as tools to exert political pressure on other states.

¹ *Non-refoulement* is prohibited not only under the ECHR, but also the Convention Against Torture and the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights - UN treaties that have been ratified by all Council of Europe member states. It is also prohibited under the Refugee Convention, which has been ratified by 43 Council of Europe member states. In addition, the standards set by the ECHR are ingrained in EU law, acting as a minimum standard for fundamental rights protection within the EU legal order.

[Concerns](#) have been raised that calling for guidance on instrumentalisation at this juncture amounts to improper pressure on the Court and undermines its independence and authority. This is because the states are expressing a collective stance on a matter that is currently pending before the Grand Chamber (highest judicial formation) of the Court, as it considers cases against Latvia, Lithuania and Poland concerning pushbacks on the border with Belarus.²

How can states obtain guidance?

The Declaration urges states to use the avenues already open to them to obtain guidance. These include intervening in cases as a “third party”, i.e. to present evidence or arguments before the Court, either as a single state or a group of states – a practice that the Court itself actively encourages.

The Declaration urges states to make greater use of existing networks that facilitate day-to-day cooperation [between the Court and higher national courts](#) and between [government officials and Council of Europe bodies](#).

It encourages states to consider opting into a [mechanism](#) allowing the highest national courts to request from the Court an advisory opinion (a non-binding legal opinion) to help them apply the Convention in cases pending at the domestic level.³ To date, [26 states](#) have done so. Experts [point out](#) that several states that have driven the Chişinău process, including Denmark, Italy, Poland and the UK, have not signed up to the mechanism.

Will anything change in practice as a result of the Declaration?

The Declaration is not a legally binding document and therefore does not require any specific or immediate action on the part of national authorities, the Court or any Council of Europe institution. It may, however, serve to guide future work of the Council of Europe and national authorities in this area.

The Commissioner for Human Rights, Michael O’Flaherty, has [stated](#) that the “assumption that adjusting the law or practice of the Convention and the Court ... will somehow axiomatically change practice on the ground – for instance, that it would impact irregular migratory flows – is not grounded in fact”. He called upon states to provide evidence as to the nature and scale of the migration-related challenges they face.

There is [evidence](#) that many factors can impede expulsion or extradition, including not only legal challenges but also resource constraints, administrative delays, problems in securing cooperation from countries of origin, and lack of formal returns agreements. These factors help to explain the [wide variation](#) between European states in the number of third-country nationals who are ordered to leave each year compared to the number who are actually removed.

Lord Michael German, General Rapporteur on European migration and asylum policies for the Parliamentary Assembly of the Council of Europe, [argues](#) that “international law must not become a scapegoat for domestic pressures”. This reflects a [concern](#) expressed by [international NGOs](#) that some states

² As of 15 May 2026, these cases are pending before the Grand Chamber; see [here](#) for further details.

³ Protocol No. 16 to the ECHR.

are seeking to externalise onto the Court responsibility for the pressures created by irregular migration which are, in fact, not of the Court's making and beyond its control.

Will the Declaration make it easier for states to expel foreign criminals?

Experts say the Declaration is unlikely to make an appreciable difference to the number of expulsions national authorities carry out. The Court has [consistently acknowledged](#) the difficulties that states face in combatting crime, including terrorism, underlining that states must be allowed to remove non-nationals they consider to be threats to national security and public safety, as long as this is done in accordance with the Convention.

The ECHR does not give anyone a right to enter or live in a country of which they are not a national or to become a citizen. The right of asylum is not provided for in the Convention and the Court does not examine asylum applications.

Removal will only breach the Convention in exceptional circumstances, including when it would create a serious risk of death, torture or inhuman and degrading treatment.

Interfering with private and family life through expulsion decisions is permissible under the ECHR as long as the risk of permanently cutting emotional and social ties within families is balanced against the public interest in removing dangerous individuals. The Declaration underlines that national authorities are often better placed to take such decisions, and that the Court would require strong reasons for taking a different view when the balancing exercise has been carried out in line with its case law. When national decisions consider all relevant factors in a case, the Court [generally defers](#) to them.⁴

How often does the Court handle migration cases?

[Statistics](#) show that the proportion of applications submitted to the Court which concern migration is very low. Of some 57,000 cases currently pending before the Court, around 1.5% relate to migration.⁵

Over the last ten years, the Court processed more than 440,000 applications, of which around 2% concerned migration. Of these, the Court found the vast majority (93%) to be inadmissible, i.e. it rejected them as invalid for reasons such as the failure of applicants to take their case as far as they could in their domestic system.

Of the applications concerning migration issues that were found admissible and proceeded to a judgment, the Court found a violation of the ECHR in around 460 applications in the past decade; i.e. on average, one per state per year.

What is the relevance of the Declaration to the EU Migration and Asylum Pact?

⁴ See, for example, *Fal v Spain*, No. 25828/23, 12 May 2026; more information [here](#).

⁵ 832 applications of 56,892 (as of 1 April 2026).

The [EU Migration and Asylum Pact](#) enters into force on 12 June 2026. The Pact will be implemented across all EU and Schengen states.

The Pact is a set of new rules to reform migration management, asylum procedures, and border security across the EU. Among other things it provides for accelerated border screening and returns, new criteria for entry, and reduced opportunities for individual appeals.

[Concern](#) has been expressed that the Pact will result in [human rights violations](#) at Europe’s borders through pushbacks, arbitrary detention, destitution and insufficient protection against refoulement. In this context, it is notable that the Chişinău Declaration has been adopted less than a month before the Pact enters into force.

NGOs have [stated](#) that rules governing border controls must not render inoperative or ineffective the human rights guaranteed by the Convention.

What reaction has there been to the Declaration?

The Commissioner for Human Rights [told the meeting in Chişinău](#) that the “extraordinary achievement of the modern-day human rights legal system is ... fragile”. He urged states to “insist on the universality of human rights”, as well as on the independence of the Court and of national courts, adding that states should “resolve never to instrumentalise human rights standards or institutions in the pursuit of policy goals, including policy goals in the context of migration management”.

What other issues did the foreign ministers in Chişinău discuss?

The Chişinău Ministerial is the annual meeting of member state governments. As such, the agenda is broader than just migration. Member states focused on Ukraine, in particular the establishment of the [Special Tribunal for the Crime of Aggression](#). They debated the [New Democratic Pact](#), a process to strengthen Europe’s democracies against threats such as authoritarianism, and foreign interference and manipulation of information.

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